

Risks and Difficulties: Artificial Intelligence's Impact on Academic Performance and Student Development.

Education has a promising future, thanks to Artificial Intelligence (AI), though its incorporation into schools and colleges poses certain risks. The noise around personalized learning and efficiency gains should not distract us from the possible harm AI such as chatbots and digital assistants can bring to students and educational institutions. Negotiating this powerful technology's intricacies requires recognizing its cons alongside mitigation measures. Therefore, this paper article aims to explore the techniques and offer more insights on how Artificial Intelligence has implications in various academic fields thereby compromising its integrity. The paper will examine the various challenges brought as a result of misusing artificially generated content amongst learners and academic institutions.

Onset, AI-generated content such as personalized question content and AI-generated presentations have shown a wide range of discrepancies and an amplified bias as data have been majorly associated with discrimination. One such concern is the biases that AI algorithms such as ChatGPT can have by default. These biases may be a reflection of training data, thus further perpetuating existing social disparities. Imagine an AI system that recommends STEM fields less often for girls based on historical data containing gender stereotypes. This serves to reaffirm existing prejudices and may limit chances for entire groups of students. As artificial intelligence (AI) advances, the use of bots and algorithms becomes less impartial and more capable of promoting cognitive biases and swaying opinions by amplifying specific information or content available to users, similar to gatekeepers in traditional media (Ikran, 2023). AI needs no such connotation of objectivity, but readiness to monitor it so as not to underscore academic gaps. As

per Ikran (2023), Finland has shown that incorporating digital literacy into education is a high priority. In 2014, the country introduced a college course called "anti-fake news," which taught students how to recognize manipulated information on the internet, such as deep-fakes and the use of bots.

Furthermore, Artificial Intelligence has proven weaknesses in privacy Concerns and Data Security like theft of identification caused by data breaches and unethical use of confidential data by unauthorized parties. This has been a result of the overreliance on AI in the education sector. This indicates that it would collect massive volumes of students' data for analysis. The fact that a lot of sensitive information about students' performance in class as well as their conduct and other personal details can easily be breached leaves too much to be desired. There could always be an infringement upon privacy through poor data security thus endangering the learners. Katsamakas et al (2023), denote that, when confidential information is transmitted using publicly available Artificial Intelligence chatbots such as ChatGPT-4, ChatGPT-3.5, and Google Bard's Gemini, it may leak. It is possible that malicious actors would use the data leak to target students, rendering them vulnerable to cyberattacks. However, this calls for a delicate balance between using data to improve teaching while also protecting students' privacy which has become a major challenge in today's learning institutions that are looking forward to maintaining trust and compliance with various privacy regulations. This can be performed by establishing a secure messaging domain that ensures the safe transfer of voice, photo, and message content to the server hosting the chatbot. It also necessitates security considerations in data exchanges. Furthermore, the domain must prioritize the user's data on the backend, which determines how the data is handled, saved, and delivered on the server (Hasa et al, 2021).

Overreliance on Technology is another major issue. Nonetheless, while Artificial Intelligence could make learning more enjoyable, overreliance on technology may negatively affect the social and emotional growth of pupils. Acquisition of knowledge does not suffice for meaningful future lives but involves the development of interpersonal skills such as critical thinking and creativity among others. A lot of dependence on tools such as Gamification, AI translation, and Intelligent Tutoring Systems will result in fewer interactions between teachers and pupils thereby supporting half-baked individuals who cannot think outside the box. Intrinsic motivation, which is required for persistent educational success, is mostly derived from a desire to learn and personal interests. Students' intrinsic motivation may suffer if AI becomes highly prescriptive or regulates the learning process, making them feel compelled to adopt a predetermined course (Moybeka et al, 2023).

Moreover, the emergence of cutting-edge technologies like Artificial Intelligence has negatively impacted job displacement for educators. There are concerns regarding job losses among educators due to the adoption of artificial intelligence into the education system. The use of automation to handle administrative duties, grading, or some teaching responsibilities may in the future downsize the demand for human educators. Gocen & Aydemir (2021) writing about the role of Artificial Intelligence in education and schools, asserts that more individuals have a firm standing that the future holds minimal opportunities for the teachers in learning institutions and yet vast chances for robotic assistants. In akin to the opinion, Gocen & Aydemir (2021) designate that teaching as a white color job in the existing context will not survive any longer, and that educators should seek another alternative on mentor contracts, guidance on lifelong skills, aiding their learners on the effective interaction and majoring on how to square out life problems by their students. AI can speed up work; yet, it must be seen as a complimenting factor rather than a

replacement on behalf of educators too. Institutions need to manage this change with care by creating room for growth and development, ensuring that the human element remains imperative in education as well as upskilling opportunities.

In addition, Artificial Intelligence is a great non-transparent since many AI algorithms are "black boxes" meaning their decision-making processes are not easily understandable. Vincent-Lancrin, & Van der Vlies, (2020) confirm that some Artificial Intelligence techniques which include deep learning, have posed challenges concerning explanations. The lack of explainability has forced countries like France to renounce the use of some forms of algorithms in public decision-making since it is extremely difficult to explain them to a lay audience. The lack of transparency in AI used in educational systems also raises concerns about accountability and the ability to challenge or question decisions made by these systems. For example, no explanation is given when one gets automated feedback from software like automated grading which hampers learning while negating the usefulness of feedback itself due to a lack of insight into its basis. Rosell (2023), argued that lack of transparency in AI affects confidence beyond those directly affected. However, it also has an impact on the wider public's confidence in AI and perceptions of the validity of public-sector judgments.

Also, the Digital Divide has posed a great threat to the integrity of education. This is evident in the equity issues such as access to technology become more pertinent as AI becomes more integrated into education settings where the divide between digital 'haves' and 'have-nots' exists. This means that students who do not possess devices or have a poor internet connection or advanced AI tools could face disadvantages relative to those with more opportunities. A significant proportion of students are unable to supply the data required to construct and validate the

algorithms that guide instruction and other decisions due to a lack of access to the gear, software, and connectivity required to use digital learning platforms. When students from low-income households, students with special needs, or students from rural regions have continuous access, a representation gap occurs, Dieterle (2022). It can be difficult to narrow social disparities, which are connected with education in case of different technological opportunities.

Additionally, thorny Issues have become one of the ethical challenges in using AI in educational contexts when it comes to decision-making mechanisms that affect students' academic lives. Guan, Dong, & Zhao (2022), stresses that more serious ethical issues in technology may occur as a result of technological ambiguity, as well as data incompleteness and inadequacy, which can contribute to bias in decision-making. This calls for a closer examination of issues regarding favoritism, accountability, and unanticipated outcomes due to reliance on algorithms. For instance, adopting AI in college admissions or directing students' career choices could create unintentional biases and limit options for some individuals. All colleges are required by law to have ethical regulations that outline how these AI applications should be developed for education purposes with an emphasis on integrity and openness.

In conclusion, similar to a brittle bionetwork, education hinges on interpersonal relationships, trust, along with openness to survive. Although AI holds forth hope for a bright future, these essential components could be punctured by its thorns. Data security turns into a delicate butterfly, privacy becomes a walled garden, and educators face the threat of being replaced. The "black box" method is alluring, but real comprehension is still obscure. The digital gap is a long-standing issue that affects equality in the hunt for knowledge. It also raises ethical concerns about our decisions and how they affect the minds of future generations. Rather than

giving up, we should see these problems as opportunities for personal growth and productive dialogue that will help us defend privacy and strengthen data security. We make sure that teachers continue to be invaluable mentors by fostering creativity and critical thinking. The way forward will become clearer when algorithms are deconstructed and responsible AI development is encouraged. Finally, we can make sure AI deepens rather than splits the foundations of education by bridging the digital gap and tackling ethical issues with compassion and discernment. By doing this, we foster a future in which technology coexists peacefully with the human spirit, fostering not only academic achievement but also the essence of learning itself.

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